

INDOOR PLANTS THAT CANNOT BE USED IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8011117>

Annotation. The article deals with the correct use of flowers grown as ornamental plants in preschool educational institutions, the ability to choose them correctly, as well as the specific characteristics of some popular ornamental plants.

Key words: succulent, atmosphere, oxygen, poisonous substance.

As you know, since there are a large number of young children on the territory of preschool educational institutions, the main attention is paid to their healthy formation, both mental and physical. In this case, the influence of the environment is very great, and the level of illumination of each small room, their equipment and even their decoration should not have a negative impact on the health of the children of the institution. In many organizations and institutions, including preschool educational institutions, indoor plants are used for decorative purposes. But can all ornamental plants be used in children's rooms?

The type, number and characteristics of landscape plants vary, and most of them have the ability to purify the air and enrich it with oxygen. But some indoor plants cause allergies in people, and some of them emit various odors and toxic substances.

Sansevieria is a succulent plant that many people like because of its beautiful, bright leaves, suitable for any room design and does not require special care. This flower cleanses the atmospheric air from toxic substances such as benzene and trichloroethylene, humidifies the air, optimizes the biological function of the body.

The presence of 2-3 sansevieria plants in the room will improve its ecological condition. But it is not recommended to put this flower in a room where children sleep. For example:

1. It has strong energy, can make children relax and fall asleep.
2. The leaves contain the poisonous substance saponin, and they are used as a diuretic and laxative.
3. The leaves contain a poisonous substance - saponin, which is used as a diuretic and laxative.

Geranium is a common flowering plant cultivated mainly because of its beautiful flowers. This ornamental plant can be grown both as a houseplant in a flower bed and as an ornamental plant in the garden. This unpretentious plant can be found in almost all institutions due to its resistance to drought and direct sunlight. Since it contains essential oil, it is used in folk medicine for the treatment of various diseases, and sometimes in cosmetology. But it is not always recommended to put this flower in the nursery: some people, especially children, may have allergic reactions. For example: cough, sneezing, runny nose, even Quincke's edema.

To allergenic plants that emit pungent odors, you can also add oleander, alocasia and azalea.

Ficus is a perennial tree or shrub grown in floriculture because of its beautiful ornamental leaves. In our country, several species of it are grown: rubber-bearing ficus or elastic ficus, Benjamin ficus, Lyrat ficus, Binnedica ficus and Microcarp ficus. They do not require excessive lighting and are suitable for any room design. Enriches the room with oxygen, cleans and humidifies the air. The plant contains a substance that causes bronchial asthma, and precautions should be taken before placing it in the children's room (Fig. 1).

Sansevieria	Geranium	Ficus
Dieffenbachia	Cactus	Alocasia

Dieffenbachia is an exotic plant of South American origin. This is one of the most popular plants due to its rapid growth, beautiful leaves, as well as the fact that it does not require special care and is suitable for almost any interior. When the juice of this plant gets on the skin and into the eyes, it causes swelling, itching and burning. It should be kept away from people with allergies, small children and pets. Ingestion of leaves causes serious poisoning and even anaphylactic shock.

Pachypodium and **cactus** are succulent plants that can be found in almost all organizations and institutions due to their resistance to water and light, the environment and conditions. It is also important to protect them from children because of their appearance - thorns.

Alocasia is an ornamental large-leaved perennial plant, and in folk medicine this flower is used due to the substances contained in it. This flower is poisonous and should be avoided. Otherwise, diarrhea can cause various negative effects.

In addition to the ornamental plants listed above, many more plants can be included in such a "black list". The main thing is that the correct use of flowers grown as ornamental plants in educational institutions, the ability to choose them correctly, should not adversely affect the health and safety of the pupils of this institution.

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